

An Examination of Horticultural Therapy Implications for Foster Children

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The implications of horticultural therapy and therapeutic gardening for foster communities have not been thoroughly studied. However, related literature supports a potential positive implication of this hypothesis. Horticultural therapy is beneficial for children in numerous ways; for instance, assisting foster-children specific needs and furthering the treatment of mental disorders. Defined as therapy within a garden setting, horticultural therapy mimics play therapy in that participants are encouraged to feel more comfortable with their surroundings. Therapeutic gardening refers to mindful gardening activities to promote physical and mental well-being. For the purposes of this study, “horticultural therapy” and “therapeutic gardening” will be used interchangeably.

Even with foster-specific needs, foster children still exhibit the same behaviors as any other child. Benefits of horticultural therapy for children within “standard” residencies are still prominent for foster children. Foster children also face a plethora of mental disorders; the benefits of therapeutic gardening would help alleviate these mental ailments and aid these troubled individuals. Foster children also harbor specific needs stemming from their time in the foster system. These needs can be met through horticultural therapy.

An exploration of the physiological/psychological implications of horticultural therapy and therapeutic gardening on children in group foster home care will be beneficial to many interest groups. This will benefit the foster community and current research due to the lack of research in the field of study. The foster community may experience benefits through increased mental health treatment opportunities, improving quality of life for foster children and easing operations to foster children service providers.

Horticultural Therapy for Children

The foster population is prevalent in the US with over 391,000 children and youth as of 2021 (U.S. Department of Health and Human Services [HHS]). Children with typical residencies are more likely to experience better health behaviors and lower levels of sickness (Tinsley et al., 1989). Furthermore, traditionally-homed children make better grades when having a consistent relationship with caregivers and are more likely to carry out positive relationships with their peers (Epstein et al., 1987; Ladd et al., 1995). Foster children are typically stricken with more ailments than their traditionally-homed counterparts; a study by Pholihronakis found that 18%-22% of the general population suffers from mental ailments while the foster community may be upwards to 80% (2008).

Horticultural therapy has the potential for being a positive treatment option for children since gardening simultaneously improves mental and physical well-being. Therapeutic gardening leads to reductions in depression, anxiety, and body mass index and increases satisfaction, quality of life, and sense of community, all of which are beneficial for a child's growth (Francis, 1995). Moreover, time spent within horticulture increases levels of resting, meditation and relaxation. Therapeutic gardening can reduce anxiety by lowering cortisol levels and regulating the nervous system. Self-esteem is also improved through gardening by enhancing children's autonomy and control over plants (Community Child Guidance Clinic).

There are long term benefits associated with gardening as well. Many adults remember both the flora and playing within the garden. Water features and physical structures such as fountains and benches are memorable since they lead to additional play. Gardens act as a place to think, which is beneficial as it allows for reflection. "Un-gardening" refers to unstructured play within a garden. Un-gardening is especially impactful, allowing children to experience a less

structured form of play (Francis, 1995). These positive memories and practice of mindfulness are beneficial to children's development.

Mindfulness is a key feature of therapeutic gardening, as per Francis's findings. Mindfulness practices are typically well-received by children, allowing them to be more in touch with their thoughts and emotions. Mindfulness helps to alleviate stress, teach regulation techniques to help manage difficult emotions, and deepen emotional understanding and emotional stability (Zelazo & Lyons, 2012). These practices have been tested through small-scale implementations. Specifically, adolescents report higher levels of calmness and better behavior as a result of having plants in their classroom. Plants act as an outlet for students to tend to. This has led to increased empathy group unity (Bahamonde, 2019).

Horticultural Therapy on Mental Disorder

Therapeutic gardening acts as a natural, side-effect-free treatment for those suffering from psychological implications. Gardening helps promote calming, restorative effects on participants and the repair of brain cells while delivering additional oxygen to the body (G. Chen et al., 2021). Socialization within therapeutic gardens also has positive benefits on those suffering from mental ailments. Movement and the outdoor presence of gardening can allow for better sleep in participants, which is known to help alleviate mental burden (H. Chen, 2021)

Generally, horticultural therapy has been an extremely effective treatment option for PTSD. Natural therapy has been used on other non-foster populations such as the military. There was much success and praise in that regard, highlighting the appeal of horticultural therapy for PTSD (Poulsen et al., 2016). This is a historical treatment as well, with cases being created in this manner since World War II (Marcus & Sachs, 2013). Foster children may find similar relief for their PTSD symptoms through horticultural therapy. Therapeutic gardening may help to alleviate symptoms, allowing foster children to hold a new calming, productive outlook.

Foster Child Needs

With over 391,000 children and youth in the foster care system, foster children play a prominent role in the United States population (HHS). Compared to children in normal care, foster children require escalated medical care to stay healthy due to their previous living conditions (Steenbakkers et al., 2018). Mentorship, resources, stable housing, and financial management are all needs reported by foster children, adult supporters, and staff members. Mentorship may be found through therapy, where therapists provide useful insight into behaviors and self-improvement and reflection (Mares, 2010). Horticultural therapy is a potential solution to this because it offers a unique opportunity for therapy in a low stress environment. These positive effects are beneficial to foster children, highlighting the physical and mental needs laid out by Mares's research (G. Chen et al., 2021).

A main foster-specific need these children may encounter is a desire for consistency. Consistency has been found as a major emotional need for foster children. Foster children require a consistent parental figure to guide and nurture for the best raising opportunities (Harden, 2004). This same principle may hold for non-human interactions. For instance, changes in residence may inflate feelings of inconsistency and contribute to higher anxiety rates, leading to a desire for consistency to uphold positive benefits for the community. Therapeutic gardening offers this sense of consistency and control needed by these vulnerable populations (Community Child Guidance Clinic). Therapeutic gardening also allows for future planning where participants are concerned with gardening matters (i.e. flora care). This creates an increased sense of control within patients who may feel a lack of control in other aspects of their life. Through control over the plants and oneself in the garden, feelings of control and consistency return to prominence within the community. This concludes therapeutic therapy as a quality option for in foster care or those suffering from similar ailments as those in foster care.

Mental Disorders within Foster Populations

Upwards of 80% of foster children have mental struggles while 18%-22% of the general population has mental struggles, highlighting the need for adequate therapeutic practice (Polihronakis, 2008). Children within the foster care system are more likely to be sad and aggressive, stemming from adverse negative upbringing conditions. Polihronakis also finds that 56.7% of foster children experience some form of maltreatment (2008). Adverse situations and experiences in childhood have led to effects on the human stress response (Hunter, 2011). These effects can appear as early as infancy, highlighting the extent of the time affected. The experience of neglect can have a strong negative impact on a child, leading to post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). Children who tested high for severe PTSD tended to experience more maltreatment than children who tested less severe; less severe cases typically stemmed from neglect rather than maltreatment (Sölva et al., 2020). Contrarily, Lehmann et al. found rates of depression and anxiety within foster children to be negligible (2013). However, one in two foster children still experience a behavioral or physiological disorder with approximately one in five children suffering from a behavior disorder, ADHD, or an attachment disorder (Lehmann et al., 2013).

Good treatment for these negative traits may lead to a more satisfactory life (Gadeyne et al., 2004). Untreated, long-term, persistent stress in childhood may have major effects on health in adulthood (Shonkoff et al., 2009). These effects can range from lower achievement levels to higher mortality rates (Anda et al., 2009; Danese & McEwen, 2012). Minimizing these effects and determinants through treatment may increase life satisfaction, which highlights the need for early intervention.

Method

Research Approach

This study addresses the potential implications of therapeutic gardening and horticultural therapy on foster children living in group home populations. This study examined determining characteristics of foster children, investigating the extent to which these characteristics cause need and answering if horticultural therapy meets these criteria. The research approach of choice is semi-structured interviews; they allow for a broad exploration of interviewee knowledge. The prior experiences of horticultural therapy may cause the researcher to hold prejudiced beliefs that may sway the results of this study. Due to the nature of this study, interviewees may have provided biased results based on their own knowledge and experiences with horticultural therapy/therapeutic gardening.

This study assumed that there will be a consequent correlation if a foster child meets a certain criteria. This study follows a transitive style of reasoning: if $A=B$ and $B=C$, then $A=C$. For example, if a foster child suffers from mental ailments, and horticultural therapy is beneficial for said ailments, the assumption is made that horticultural therapy is beneficial for the foster child. The study assumed that interviews were answered accurately. It was assumed that the method was most effective to answer the research question.

Research Design

The discussion of method led to the choice of a qualitative method for this study. Semi-structured interviews were used for data collection. The interviews implemented open-ended questions that allowed for the individual input and thought of each of the interviewees. These interviews primarily took place via video chat for feasibility. There was one exception due to medical concerns that lead to a correspondence over email. Interviews lasted

between 10 and 30 minutes based on the length of contributions from interviewees. This study totaled four interviews.

This method coincides with additional studies such as Bahamonde (2019). In this study, Bahamonde conducted interviews to formulate how plants in the school setting positively impact students. Since students were considered a protected group, Bahamonde interviewed guidance counselors who worked directly with these students. Qualitative open-ended interviews with these counselors allowed for a better understanding of impacts on students. This interview format was adopted for the current study to protect foster children while best understanding their needs.

This study holds potential limitations in research, such as determining the implications of age, regarding these populations. The prior understandings of horticultural therapy may have caused the researcher to hold prejudiced beliefs that may sway the results of this study. This study interviewed a small population that is specific to ██████████ County, which could cause these results to be inapplicable on a large scale. Survey members may not have provided objective feedback due to personal bias or false information.

Participants/Subjects

Interview samples were chosen by the researcher to ensure high-quality results. These individuals were selected non-randomly to ensure educated research availability. Two interviewees were past foster case workers and two interviewees were current workers within therapeutic practices involving foster children at the time of interview.

Recruitment for interviews took place over email interaction with interview candidates. All participants consented prior to this study. Interviews with audiovisual recordings clearly stated their consent to the recording at the beginning of recording. There were no safety considerations above an everyday risk.

Procedures

The interviewees were selected and contacted via text and email to request participation. A standardized message was used for each invite, as seen in Appendix A. Interviews were conducted individually with the researcher and the interviewee. The researcher then asked a series of predetermined questions to determine the needs and experiences of the foster children with whom the interviewee worked with. Before the questions regarding horticultural therapy, interviewees were educated on the biases of the subject through a short reading. This reading and the interview questions are available in Appendix C. Interviews were approximately 10 to 30 minutes in length with variance in accordance with the amount of participation from the interviewee.

Participation was on a voluntary basis; participants could stop responding at any time. All participants indicated consent prior to this study. Participation and recording consent was established at the beginning of the call via the statement in Appendix B. Interviewees were aware of the use of the Zoom recording devices. Interview data was confidential to preserve the validity of the study. Interviewees consented to release of identifying data like occupation to show the validity and significance of their interview data.

Analysis

Data was analyzed categorically through qualitative analysis. Interviewee data was collected via audiovisual recording then transcribed using YouTube's transcription feature. Interviews were analyzed through thematic analysis to discover trends. This data was used to conclude determining characteristics of foster children, determining the extent to which these characteristics cause need, and answering if horticultural therapy meets these criteria. The researcher began by identifying important aspects of each interview, then coding the aspects into

corresponding themes. These themes were then defined. Themes were compared with previous literature to see how horticultural therapy can address theme-specific challenges.

Results

Four common themes were identified from all interviews. These themes include physical instability, internal emotional dysregulation, external physical neglect, and external emotional neglect. These terms are defined in Table 1. The full interviews may be found within Appendix D.

Table 1

Definition of Themes

Theme	Definition
Physical instability	Effect of consistently varying location and experiences.
Internal emotional dysregulation	Intense feelings/mental distressed harbored within a child (ex: impulse control, aggression and anxiety)
External physical neglect	Lack of necessary physical care for foster children (ex: education and medical care)
External emotional neglect	Lack of emotional attention/counseling needed to provide emotional dexterity and resilience

These themes were founded from input given by the four interviewees. This input and the corresponding theme was explored in Table 2. Table 2 houses highlights of the interviewees' discussion. Many interviewees explored topics that reflected all four of the themes.

Table 2

Participant Response Data

Participant #	Key Experiences/Inputs	Corresponding Themes
1	Foster children commonly struggle with impulse control along with emotional dysregulation. Many also experience aggressiveness as a result of turmoil.	Emotional Dysregulation
	Due to transitions and placements, foster children commonly have their education changed or interrupted. This leads to undereducation.	External physical neglect
2	High rates of anxiety are prevalent in foster children.	Emotional Dysregulation
	Foster children commonly lack a sense of place. This leads to a lack of consistency	Physical Instability
	Children require age appropriate explanations of why they are in foster care and what will happen in foster care in order to feel safe.	External emotional neglect
3	Children often lack health care services. Issues such as toothaches are often left unresolved due to improper support. Food insecurity is also a prevalent issue while fostering.	External physical neglect

Participant #	Key Experiences/Inputs	Corresponding Themes
	Foster children are often not emotionally supported. Foster children commonly struggle with issues including trauma and Posttraumatic Stress Disorder. Therapy is a beneficial outlet for foster children.	External emotional neglect
4	Foster children deserve a stable home environment.	Physical Instability
	Children need a “healthy” home where they have access to essential care, such as shelter, food and support.	External physical neglect

As previously discussed, this study interviewed four different members of various networks involving foster children. Of this study, two interviewees were past case workers. The other two were currently working in a therapeutic setting involving foster children. All participants were educated in child well-being and familiar with foster child needs. All participants shared sentiments that foster children naturally face adverse conditions within their experience in both foster care and moving forward within life. Issues such as lack of consistency, lack of proper medical or educational opportunity, and high rates of mental turmoil were common throughout all interviews. These common issues lead to the four themes of analysis

(physical instability, internal emotional dysregulation, external physical neglect, and external emotional neglect).

Intervention was positively discussed with suggestions for increased education for foster providers. By educating those who work directly with foster children on the child's needs, interviewees suggest resulting improved experiences for foster children. All participants responded that horticultural therapy, in their professional opinion, seemed like a potential solution to meet these children's needs. Participants were educated on the basis of horticultural therapy prior to questions involving horticultural therapy's application. Interviewee's cited concerns such funding and resources as potential concerns in regard to a horticultural therapeutic approach. Lack of interest was additionally a cited concern with participants questioning the initial interest of foster children to gardening.

Analysis

All participants shared sentiments that foster children naturally face adverse conditions, thus creating a need for intervention. Intervention was positively discussed, with suggestions for bettering foster conditions. After first analysis, this study's question shifted from if there is a need for horticultural therapy to if horticultural therapy would effectively meet the needs of foster children.

The four themes of analysis - physical instability, internal emotional dysregulation, external physical neglect, and external emotional neglect - correspond with horticultural therapy practices. Physical instability correlates to a need for stability, which horticultural therapy offers. Therapeutic gardening allows for participants to feel more connected with oneself. Gardening allows for a self-controlled environment, which can be appreciated by those struggling with constant environmental changes (Community Child Guidance Clinic). This concludes

horticultural therapy as a quality option for foster care due to its benefit within sustaining consistency.

Internal emotional dysregulation corresponds with a need for mindfulness. Interviewees reported signs of dysregulation in foster children such as increased aggressiveness and anxiety rates. This confirmed the conclusions of existing research, such as Hunter (2011). Therapeutic gardening acts as a treatment option for those suffering from psychological implications. Therapeutic gardening acts to regulate the nervous system, providing a much needed sense of relief to participating parties (G. Chen et al., 2021). Additionally, physical movement and the outdoor nature of gardening can help alleviate mental burden (H. Chen, 2021). Mindfulness, found within gardening, helps deepen emotional stability and understanding (Zelazo & Lyons, 2012). Mindfulness practices are typically well-received by children, allowing them to benefit from emotional regulation.

External physical neglect was arguably the least applicable to horticultural therapy. Participants regarded medical and dental care as the leading cause of need of intervention, followed by education. These practices require professional intervention in areas that a therapeutic provider would not be able to effectively address. However, therapeutic gardening does offer some intervention. Gardening improves physical health leading to reduction in body mass index. Gardening also increases in life satisfaction, quality of life and sense of community, which are beneficial for child development. (Francis, 1995). Education could be addressed through educational gardening experiences; however, it would not be beneficial enough to be considered an effective treatment option.

External emotional neglect may be effectively addressed within horticultural therapy. Mentorship was a significant need as reported by foster children, adult supporters, and staff members in Mares (2010). Mentorship may be found through therapy, where therapists may

provide useful insight into behaviors and self-improvement and reflection. Support groups were also discussed in Participant 1's interview. Group therapy and support groups are beneficial to foster children by increasing their sense of understanding and safety while in a difficult situation. Bahamonde conducted a study where therapeutic gardening acted as an outlet for the students - the students were eager to care for the plants (2019). This has additionally led to increased empathetic practices and group unity. This can be replicated and reproduced in a therapeutic gardening setting where foster children have the chance to bond with one another.

Discussion

This study addresses the potential implications of therapeutic gardening and horticultural therapy on foster children living in group home populations. To do so, this study followed a thought path of determining characteristics of foster children, determining the extent to which these characteristics cause need, and answering if horticultural therapy meets these criteria. Semi-structured interviews were used for data collection. These interviews took place primarily via video chat to allow for ease of operations. The interviews were open ended with guiding questions that allowed for the individual inputs and thoughts of each of the interviewees. Recording and participation consent was established at the beginning of the recording. The researcher then asked questions tailored to the experience and knowledge of the interview.

Within this study, four major themes were discovered through qualitative analysis. Physical instability, internal emotional dysregulation, external physical neglect, external emotional neglect were common themes founded within this study. Physical instability refers to the effects on foster children when experiencing a consistently varying location and experience. Internal emotional dysregulation corresponds with intense feelings or mental distress harbored within a child, for example, impulse control, aggression and anxiety. External physical neglect refers to lack of necessary physical care for foster children like education and medical care.

External emotional neglect refers to the lack of emotional attention and counseling needed to provide emotional dexterity and resilience.

The study concluded that horticultural therapy has the potential to be beneficial to foster child populations. The four major themes discovered in this study - physical instability, internal emotional dysregulation, external physical neglect, external emotional neglect - relate to the existing research on these topics. Physical instability correlates to a need for stability, which horticultural therapy offers. Therapeutic gardening offers this sense of consistency and control needed by foster children (Community Child Guidance Clinic). Internal emotional dysregulation corresponds with a need for mindfulness, which can also be treated within horticultural therapy (Francis, 1995). External physical neglect may be addressed through the health benefits that gardening brings. External emotional neglect may be addressed through therapy and group work within therapeutic gardening.

Limitations

Due to time and resource constraints, only four individuals were interviewed. Despite the quality of these interviews, additional interviews may produce a greater variety of results. More perspectives would bring forth a deeper level of understanding that comes with a more comprehensive worldview. Additionally, interviews may have been biased. Since these interviews were open-ended with guiding questions, the wording and intonation of the questions presented may lead to skewed conclusions. This was overcome by the final question asking for limitations in this study and other inputs. Additionally, these suggestions and practices are not one-size-fits-all. Different individuals benefit from different forms of therapy; what helps one child may not help others. Horticultural therapy and therapeutic gardening may be hypothesized to benefit foster children as a whole, but individual experiences and personalities lead to different

benefit retention rates. In application, it would be essential to try multiple methods and applications of therapy.

It would be beneficial to directly interview current or former foster children to discuss their needs. Since foster children are a protected group, it was not feasible to directly interview foster children. This is due to protection constraints on current foster children and a found lack of interest in past foster children. Best case scenario, foster children would hold direct opinions on their needs and the application of horticultural therapy on their interest group. Since foster children are the subjects of this therapy, it is important for them to be onboard with the treatment plan.

Application of therapeutic gardening and horticultural therapy would vary due to changes in population. Different ages may benefit to different degrees with this design. Interests and hobbies of participants to this therapy may also influence results. As previously stated, different therapy techniques work best on different populations. An exploration of different techniques on different populations may lead to results that would greatly benefit certain populations in practice.

Implications

This study provides a new perspective that builds upon the existing literature within the field. Previously, there was little to no research on the implications of horticultural therapy for foster children. Other studies may directly experiment and investigate real-world practices of this theoretical research. Future research can work directly with foster children to find specific beneficial activities. Examples of these activities would be different mindfulness exercise types within therapeutic gardening. Group versus individual counseling would be an additional genre to research.

Conclusion

These findings agree with the initial hypothesis of this experiment - there could be a positive implication while exploring horticultural therapy treatment for foster children. The findings of this study agreed with the previous literature on this subject. This study helped contribute to bridging a gap between a theoretical investigation of horticultural therapy for foster children and an actual process of this research. This study identifies a need and a potential resolution to such need. It would be worthwhile to pursue an experimental approach to see if this approach could work in practice. An application of this research could help countless families within the foster system, case workers, therapists, and others working with foster children.

Ultimately, this study has created a starting point for experimental exploration of the benefits of horticultural therapy and therapeutic gardening for foster children. This study has set a precedent for theoretical findings in the field, bringing forth a hypothesis to be explored in more depth as an experimental study. This study has the potential to positively impact thousands of foster children and providers nationwide. This research is of great value and interest to the foster care community and should continue to be researched as an application of therapeutic techniques to better the lives of those afflicted by foster care.

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Appendix A

Interview Request Email Template

Hello (*name*)!

I am [REDACTED], a member of [REDACTED] High School. I received your contact information from [REDACTED]. I am an AP Research Capstone student. In this program, we develop and explore a research study with a thesis of our choosing. My thesis is on the potential implications of horticultural therapy for foster children.

As per your experience as a caseworker, I would love to find a time for an interview (via Zoom) with you to gather your thoughts and insights. Interviews have 5 open ended questions and last approximately 15 minutes. If you are not available for an interview, we can also explore a written correspondence over email.

Please let me know if you are interested. Further questions can be directed to me at [REDACTED]@gmail.com or my AP Capstone Research teacher, [REDACTED], at [REDACTED]@[REDACTED].org.

Thank you!

[REDACTED]

Appendix B

Consent Form

The purpose of this study is to explore the potential implications of horticultural therapy/therapeutic gardening on foster children. The interview contains 5 questions and should take no longer than 20 minutes, and there are minimal to no risks involved. Your participation is completely voluntary and there will be no negative consequences if you decide not to participate. You may stop participating at any time and you may choose not to answer any specific question. Your answers are confidential; no identifying data will be released. Responses will be recorded via audio/video recording software in order for data preservation. No recordings will be released.

If you have any questions about this study, contact the researcher, [REDACTED], at [REDACTED]@gmail.com or the AP Capstone Research teacher, [REDACTED], at [REDACTED]@[REDACTED].org.

By verbally acknowledging this consent form and continuing to answer, you agree to the terms stated.

Appendix C

Interview Questions and Resources

Introductory Questions

What is your relationship to foster children?

What is your relationship to horticultural therapy?

Interview Questions

1. What are some of the perceptions held regarding foster child wellbeing? Elaborate on current foster challenges. What is the best course of action to address these needs?

Background Information

Therapeutic gardening/horticultural therapy is a therapy treatment that involves mindful gardening exercises. These experiences have been shown to reduce stress while promoting other health benefits. Gardening improves mental health while improving physical health. Self esteem is improved through gardening through children's autonomy and control over plants.

Mindfulness helps both manage stress while learning regulation techniques to help manage emotions later.

Interview Questions (cont.)

2. What is the best course of action to address these needs? Are horticultural therapy practices appropriate to address these challenges? Is there a perceived need for intervention?

3. What challenges do you foresee happening within this approach? What response do you foresee?

Appendix D

Interview Transcripts

Interview 1 Transcription

I think that should work and then I'm just going to do my backup recording just in case because I'll be real I'm not a very Zoom person so want to make sure I have everything I need. Awesome, okay, so I'm gonna read you a really quick consent form if you can just verbally say, "I consent to participate in this survey" afterwards just so all the practices are checked and everything's good. okay so the purpose of the study is to oh oh I'll show these to we'll be so cute hi I'm heading Miss Conon's closet right now oh love it that's so awesome okay the purpose of the study is to explore the potential implications of hor cultural therapy therapeutic name on foster children living in group home setting the interview contains five questions and should take no longer than 15 minutes and they're minimal to know risk involved your participation is completely voluntary and there will be no negative consequences if you decide not to participate you may stop participating at any time and your data will be released responses will be recorded via audio video recording software in order to for data preservation no recordings will be released if you have any questions about the study please contact the researcher [REDACTED] [REDACTED] or AP or the AP caps research teacher my Cononconon. devard schools.org this consent form has been carefully read and fully understood by the ccle okay so now you just I consent yes

I consent

Awesome thank you so much okay so I have a few introductory questions and then we can

get right into it so what is your relationship with foster children

i'm currently I am working as a registered clinical social work intern which means I have my masters in social work and I'm working towards licensed so I can be like an independent therapist so it's a weird title it's really long so it's usually abbreviated sometimes so I see a couple foster kids one-on-one in therapy ones that have actually been placed so none that have been in they've been in group homes in the past and then in previous jobs I've had I have worked with children who were on hospice care who lived in a group home just on a one-on-one basis for like anticipatory grief support because they're you know they had like a what's the word a terminal illness and stuff like that so I've had a few different roles where I've worked with kids in foster care just providing emotional support awesome

I just realized I put group CARE into the consent form I changed the project it's not looking at group CARE so works out but yeah I feel like you're good all around you kind of know kids you know what's H up so I felt like you'd be a really great person to interview for this and then have you heard of Slash what's your relationship with horticultural therapy

I've never you know like actually done Horticultural therapy one-on-one with any of the kids I think it's a great concept personally I love like you know gardening and stuff it's very therapeutic so when I read was your that was your research project I was like o that actually gives me a good idea maybe I can start utilizing that with some of my kids because a lot of them do have impulse control issues and so a lot of times it comes out as aggression some will run away from home when they're angry so having an activity like that where it's like they have

something to take care of I think sounds really like calming and good for

Them

I very much agree that's why of my projects on this so works out so yeah we're just going to get started with some of a actual like more diving deep questions now so what are some

perceptions held against foster child wellbeing so if you could elaborate on current foster child challenges what can a child expect to struggle with in foster care and kind of how does that

Impact them

um from what I've seen and just there you know learning about child welfare and stuff one of the biggest things foster children struggle with is completing their education due

to their unstable like home life a lot of them Jump Around because they have the behavioral issues because of their like you know difficult childhoods and they have trouble finishing

school they're like attainment is you know pretty low and those behavioral issues that kind of go alongside with that is I'm sorry my voice sounds so bad

you're absolutely fine

um you know like those impulse control problems some aggressiveness emotional dysregulation

you know things like that and it really impacts their ability to like you know form friendships

and bonds and yeah it's they're they're definitely a very they're a population that struggles a lot

and getting them the help they need can be a struggle because it kind of needs to be on all four

fronts like the foster parents need to be on board School needs to be on board whatever like

mental health support like to be in full communication so it really it can be a lot sometimes but

um

yeah you actually kind of started talking about my next question here so is there a perceived need for intervention and then kind of how would we best address these needs we discussed with and just kind of what is the application approach to kind of help these needs

um the need?

yes the Horticultural therapy or just like how to help them how to help them in general the next question is on horror cultural therapy

okay cool Sorry

perfect you're doing great really

um I've found that peer support groups are really good for kids in the foster care system to know that they're like there's a b they know there's a lot of other kids in the foster care system but actually organized groups is really good for them to relate to each other to understand each other's emotions know they're not alone it normalizes what they're going through in one-on-one like therapy what I found is helpful is rehearsing coping skills so with one of my clients right now they're pretty they're pretty young they're less than 10 years old and they have a history of running away from home whenever they get frustrated and he's with a foster family right now so one of the coping skills is when he gets that level of anger he needs to go sit on the bean bag so we kind of act out the scenarios that make him mad he's homeschooled so it's usually School

related stuff and his anger will just like Spike so we kind of make a game out of it and just like practice doing those skills another coping skill that we practice doing is deep breathing we like do belly breathing so that's when you hold your hands on your stomach and like there's a bunch of different Brea deep breathing techniques and then bibliotherapy too I read a lot of books regarding like different emotions how to I identify them and that are like kind of interactive with the kids so that it gets them talking about their own emotions because the more they talk about it they more they're processing how it all works and it all becomes a little bit more normal in their minds and then they can connect okay I feel frustrated when this happens and my body responds in this way and that means I need to do this to prevent this from happening so it's kind of there's a lot there's a lot that we do and sometimes art therapy will just do relaxing art projects and stuff like that and a lot of the kids that I see they do have ADHD so some kids do need medication some kids don't I've met kids who they're they've come in on medication and it's been effective and but after they learn skills they don't really need it anymore and then there's kids that I have seen that are unmedicated and despite work and work and work they it's it's really difficult for them to emotionally regulate and they do need medication so that's also a need for them

yeah I'm medicated for ADHD so I get it so awesome thank you that's actually like what you're saying right now perfect for my study and it's like it's all coming together because we I've had a lot of issues get in here but so I have one more question for you here so therapeutic gardening horticulture therapy is a therapy treatment that involves mindful gardening exercises these experiences have been shown to reduce stress while promoting other health benefits and then with that being said how do you feel like horticultural therapy would potentially impact a foster child so would it be beneficial do you foresee any issues with that approach

definitely seems beneficial all of the mind like body activities focusing on physically doing something I think it's a really holistic healing way to calm down your like nervous system and feel used to that comforting feeling and then you realize you can turn to that when you're feeling a little dysregulated and stuff like that so I do think the Horticultural therapy sounds like a great idea for kids with in the foster care system it gives them a sense of responsibility helps them have a hobby that is not just like you know running around outside it's something totally different and then there's it opens to learning about a bunch of different like plants and nature and stuff and I love nature as like a calming thing I love just going outside I always think that's like the best for kids so this is just an extra thing they can do that's outside and get them in the sunlight and you know it's just all around seems like a great idea

yeah awesome okay I think that about concludes anything do you have anything additional you would like to add and have kind of on the record

um I don't think so but I think your project that's awesome you

thank you so much for your time this has been incredibly helpful you're actually my first interview and all the data for this project was supposed to be returned last week but we've had a lot of issues coming up with that so hard if you have any if you there's anything else you can always like text me any more questions thank you so much of course it was a pleasure meeting you

Interview 2 Transcription

Go Hopefully okay and then awesome

hopefully I don't cough too much because I'm trying to get over this I got you we have a bug going around over here too if you want I'm hiding in the bedroom because I have a house full of children right now that are very noisy and I can't get away anywhere else

you're absolutely fine I have two younger siblings so absolutely get it I share a room with my sister so we're currently hiding out with my brother's room so yeah here you want to get started

sure okay

so I'm gonna read you a consent form really quick if you can verbally acknowledge your consent at the end that would be amazing so the purpose of this study is to explore the potential implications of horticultural therapy therapeutic gardening on foster children this interview contains five questions that should take no longer than 20 minutes and they're minimal to no risk involved your participation is completely voluntary and there will be no negative consequences if you decide not to participate you may stop participating at any time and may choose not to answer any specific question your answers are confidential no identifying data will be released responses will be recorded via audio video recording software in order for data preservation no recordings will be released if you have any questions about this study please contact the researcher [REDACTED] at my email or the AP cstone teacher Min I always pronoun

your name [REDACTED].org I cannot pronounce her first name for the
lie for me because I know her as [REDACTED] so it always feels wrong saying her okay and then
by verbally acknowledging this form and continuing to answer you agree to both terms
stated so if you could give me

a agree okay

perfect awesome thank you okay so what is your relationship to foster children so I worked in
foster care um I used to teach at Vera in the academy and I moved to West Virginia um and the
first job that I actually took here was in foster care ah yeah yeah um so I've known a lot of foster
parents in the past prior to that but in Florida um and I've known a lot about foster care but never
really got into it until then um so I worked in foster care as a case manager and then moved over
to be a licensing specialist um after that but that's foster care for me because when I left foster
care there was a conflict of interest to Foster while you in foster care here with the agency and
my husband and I really had end it in our hearts that we wanted to do that so we now Foster

that's awesome I'm I'm actually in my and I plan on fostering when I'm older so really cool to see
how I know yeah okay and then what is your relationship to horticultural therapy

I don't have a relationship with Horticultural therapy but I work in therapy now and I see the
benefits of nurturing um with plants and animals and foster care if that makes any sense so I
don't have anything like more specific for you other than yeah for you know for
that but I can tell you that um some of the referrals I used to get when I was in foster care they
don't really have a lot of positives about children um especially older children but like negatives

you would see a lot of times and so one of the things I look for whenever I would help with placement is to find strengths um because I remember reading a referral one time about a little boy who he had all these like bad habits and things you know like they're quick to tell about you know the things that he was doing but it also said that but the thing he loved to do was to help his mom water the plants his foster mom currently um and help feed the pets and that was his thing and if he was you know distracted in that and he' given a a task of nurturing task like that then his behaviors you know were better

so yeah that's actually exactly what I'm hoping to hear here so I'm focusing really on the if you want a little background on my project I'm focusing more on yeah it I'm focusing more on the Foster side and speaking to a bunch of casew workers to see how it theoretically would approach to um core cultural therapy because literally just as you said that's the proposed benefits for the children so we'll have a little bit more about it in a little bit with questions but it's really cool to see how it all comes together that way yeah so okay and now if we get into that actual like meaty questions what are some perceptions invol excuse me what are some of the perceptions held regarding foster child wellbeing and then if you could elaborate on kind of foster child challenges and how are some needs that they might need to be met so the first part of the question was about what they

I missed that first little bit

oh I'm sorry it's uh the what are some perceptions held regard regarding foster child well-being so like how are the foster kids doing okay so in West Virginia at any given time we have about 7,500 children in foster care yeah it's we had you know an opioid epidemic here in West Virginia

Which contributed greatly to that um that's only one you know one piece of it there are a lot of other things why kids get in foster care but um a lot of the challenges I guess whenever they come into foster care is there's no stability um and it's not just in like a home it's it's like normal things that people don't think about um like going to doctor visits you know if you get a toothache getting your needs met like that um people always think you know oh let me donate clothing and stuff like that yeah that's part of it but the emotional needs are you know also not being met like the neglect part of it that side of it um and obviously depending on what all they've been through getting them into Therapy Services is really important um I've we did emergency placements only when we first started foster care which we should only have like 48 hour placements while they're being placed into care get the call in the middle of the night kind of thing um it never did we never did that and it ended up being like 10 days or so sometimes especially for the teenagers but um and then we switched over to traditional foster care and I always worked in it as a case manager um so my perception I I walked into it with a good reality of what it looks like but then when you it's 24/7 in your own home you know you get to take on those unruly behaviors and so you see it as a case manager too um but you know like for instance one of the kids that I have now hasn't been to school for two years so it's my challenge now to you know I got her enrolled immediately into school you obviously they're behind when they come you know there's some triny issues um so that's a little bit I guess um there's you know diagnoses that pop up because because of the things that they've been through you know PTSD um they have food insecurities and a lot of different things really and they manifest it manifests differently in each child so

thank you so what would you say would be the best course of action to kind of address these needs and is there anything in particular that could help like P what a good way to word it like

basically how would you address these needs if you could kind of fix everything with one magic spell

I think in the state that I live in they usually you know and I do have something to compare to because I've lived in Florida and seen how foster care works there too versus here um the state I live in gets involved fairly quickly and they don't play so unfortunately and fortunately um that involves you know sometimes parental rights are terminated I don't see that as much as in Florida um but lots of chances are given um but there's certain Expectations by the court system to you know make some changes the for the parents to make changes in their lives or you know it leads to termination um what I would like to see I mean I guess for Florida I would I would like to see the same thing um it doesn't seem to me that well a lot of times the children's needs are overlooked like they're assigned it's a little bit different I don't know how familiar you are in the F the foster care system down there versus you know but they have in Florida they have a guardian ad litem sometimes that is assigned to them um but the guardian i' light them like at least in Bard County I know they were like voluntary positions by regular people that would step up for the job to be more or less the advocate for the child where up here the guardian I'd light him is like a paid attorney for the child so it's a little bit different but again I'll bring back my I have the knowledge from working in foster care to know kind of like how it's supposed to work versus the average foster parent who doesn't really know the ins and outs and how to advocate for their child and so I think in a perfect world there would be more understanding and training on all of that so that a foster parent can would know even how to advocate for the child um for instance one of our kids she was here nothing was like really happening with a case um good I would say um other than everything was good here at our home um but she hadn't heard from the guardian at lighten which is her attorney and she was getting frustrated you know she was a

teenager getting frustrated with the with the process of it um not knowing you know like not being told things and you know like how the case is going and that kind of thing and so I had to basically be you know like step out at I had to turn into a Karen basically and you know get on the phone and start calling and say Hey you know like this is what needs to happen and get the ball rolling for her um and really be her advocate in times where she was maybe uncomfortable you know doing for herself like just to be there for that um so education I guess important for you know foster parents get training they do get training but it's you know until they're in a situation they don't know really what to expect too I think a lot of times because the kids that are coming to your kid are not the kids that you raised so you raise your children in a certain way these aren't that so sometimes it's starting from scratch so I guess you know also more realistic training for people that wanted to Foster because I think placements terminate a lot of times people will put in notices on kids because they get a kid in their home and they're like oh my gosh you know I didn't know I don't know how to deal with this situation well there's plenty of resources out there if you know where to look you know yeah yeah okay so we're gonna touch back with our cultural therapy here thank you for your insights by the way I feel like those are really helpful if you have any questions about what I'm talking about if none of it makes sense to you just let me know because I'm passionate about it but like yeah yeah have a bit experience with the like with some of the stuff in my own like household and everything but I'm not super educated but it's really interesting to hear about as somebody who wants to eventually either adopt or Foster so it's like it's really cool to kind of see what the future could entail because that not from a selfish perspective of wanting to help people but more so like realizing how indepth and how complicated an individual is just making sure everybody gets the help needed yeah my husband and I have six children between us before we start a fmg the last one went off to college this past year and um before she left for college while she was still here we started fostering but

we're adopting two at least two of the ones that are in our home right now we're adopting and we have a mom and a daughter as well right now in our home mom

and that's so awesome okay let's kind of T back to our cultural therapy really quick so I'm going to read you a bit of a background information piece therapy through cardening cultural therapy is a therapy treatment that involves mindful gardening exercises these experienes have been shown to reduce stress while promoting other health benefits guarding improves mental health while improving physical health as well self-esteem is also improved through gardening through sorry self-esteem is also improved through children's a aut autonty and control over plans mindfulness helps both ma manage stress while learning regulation techniques to help manage emotions later I'm sorry I have a list and I've done like eight years of speech therapy still comes out when I talk a little

I don't hear it oh thank you okay so kind of with that in mind so do you feel that poor culture therapy practices could be appropriate to address these needs mentioned for foster children so kind of how is it applicable

so I do think it can it can be applicable through I mean I I work in therapy now I'm not a therapist I could be my but I'm a practice administrator for a big therapy company now here um and in mindfulness of things that we work with a lot of children um and I heard you mention that um and I think horiculture um going back I know I'm bouncing all over the place here but wores I'm going back to one of the training videos I used to do when I was a licensing specialist in foster care um I had to teach foster parents I had to train foster parents to be foster parents and one of the videos that we used to watch was of this one family and I imagine because it was

made for that purpose to train foster parents that it there I could probably send you a link if you want it might help you um that it shows a teenager is working with a foster parents on a foster parent on a rose bush and bringing it like basically back to life um and how nurturing it is like she uses the the nurturing of this plant to show the relation like the symbiotic relationship between you know his his parent going through the process of recovery and what she needs to do and also him coming back to life from all of the trauma that he had endured and making it a beautiful rose bush at the

end um meanwhile there's another little boy that enters the picture who's like five very angry lots of stuff going on and he's starts beating the rose bush that they've been nurturing and like taking out his frustrations which he's angry because he sees something beautiful that you know doesn't have that kind of thing and takes out his anger and frustration on this rose bush but then it gives them all something to work with together to get the rose bush back you know where it be like where it started too um so I think I Garden in my my own spare time when I have it um I keep a garden out back a lot people we live but it is mindfulness and it is peaceful and it is being excited about like learning to like I would run out and see when something Sprouts out of the ground you know when I plant stuff I'm like so very excited to see like when it pops up out of the ground and like I'm checking on them and I'm doing those things and I think learning to nurture especially for children that haven't had nurturing necessarily they have been neglected in some in a lot of aspects um I think it would help them give them things to be more successful with in their life especially when they if they if they have been neglected they haven't been shown you know when they're learn they're learning in the process of how to take care of something maybe not like they were taken care of learning how to do it you know

yeah thank you uh is there any kind of negatives you see to this potential approach so do you feel

like horticultural therapy fundamentally would be beneficial and if it was implemented would there be any challenges

I'm not sure of any true challenges only getting participation maybe in the beginning getting a buy in from a kid that thinks it you know like that might be boring or whatever you know you never know people's interest and I know gardening is kind of like sometimes an old person thing like a perception of you know what I'm saying yeah so just getting buy in I guess from kids to be a part of it but I really I don't see any negativity that yeah some of it you know all right do you have any other insights or information you care to have on the record here I mean I can't think of anything unless you have questions any more like any common questions to ask me I think what you're doing is great um I'm excited to see how your project turns out I hope I get to see it

Interview 3 Transcription

okay so I'm just going to read you a little consent form really quick at the end if you can verbally acknowledge your consent and continue to answer you agree to the terms stated in the mle so the purpose of this study is to explore the potential implications of horticultural therapy therapeutic gardening on foster children the interview contains five questions and should take no longer than 20 minutes and they are minimal to no risk to involved your participation is completely voluntary and there should be no negative consequences if you decide not to participate you may stop participating at any time and you may choose not to answer any specific question your answers are confidential no identifying data will be released answers will be recorded by audio video recording software in order for data preservation no recordings will be

released if you have any questions about the study please contact the researcher

██████████.com or the AP cstone teacher ██████████ School Orly acknowledging his consent form can answer to stated

I consent yes perfect

okay what is your relationship to foster children

so um my husband and I adopted um three children out of the foster care system in New Mexico so they when they were first placed in our home they were considered foster children whom we later adopted when they became available and then with that I know you're also a therapist have you been educated SL workor of foster children in the past so I have um actually not really worked with foster children in an in a therapeutic setting um I have worked with other um uh adoptive adopted children um you know what I take that back there is I apologize there is one client one client that I have worked with previously that was foster care and then adopted and I have worked for her with I have worked with her in the past okay just yeah

would you say you're kind of somewhat knowing what a foster parent child somewh somewhat what like you're aware of what a foster child would need from a therapeutic perspective

I think so yeah

that's what I would say too because you literally have fostered and adopt a foster child okay I just needed to confirm that okay and then what is your relationship to horal therapy

to what

horticultural therapy

Horticultural therapy yes um that is a very interesting um therapy I actually don't know very much about that kind of therapy that's a different kind of therapy than what I practice but I I think it sounds very interesting

perfect because this is more of a foster perspective and we'll hear a little bit about what it is and if you think it would be applicable later

okay okay

awesome so what are some of the perceptions held regarding Foster child's wellbeing so if you could elaborate on some challenges children might face in foster care and then as they're also later in life out of

so so part of it is the feeling of displacement where they're being uprooted even if it's unhealthy they're still being uprooted from their home their environment things like that oftentimes as as much as you know the the Children and Family Services try not to sometimes it in it disrupts their school life if they have to go to another school because of where they're placed in imposter care so there's a huge sense of displacement also a sense of loss again that even though it was unhealthy and they were being either abused or neglected um they've still lost what was normal to them so they're displaced they're lost um they might be confused about what happened if

depending on their age if they don't if they're not given the full story by their social worker uh there might be some confusion as to why they've been removed and then what's happening and then also worry about acceptance into this Foster family with feeling like I don't know these people yet I'm going to have to live with them for who knows how long and is it safe are they safe am I going to be happy are they going to treat me well and so there's worry about I think acceptance with with with the Foster family and feeling safe with them defin

Mak sense and then what would you say the best course of action would be to address those things from a foster parent standpoint or a therapeutic standpoint um if you want to give a mixup all that would be really interesting

so I feel like addressing each of those things I feel like someone explaining to them in an age appropriate manner what happened so if they are if they're going to be too young then um obviously that wouldn't be appropriate but giving them information as is age appropriate um and kind of stating as best they can what happened and why they're in care and why this why this is the safest thing and then just acknowledging I understand that you probably feel like you know you've lost your home I understand that you feel like that you've lost your family I understand that you feel like that you've lost your school all those are really important things here are things that we're trying to do to help you feel better about those things and in regard to the Foster family really doing things to show and say to the foster child you are loved you are accepted you are going to be taken care of you are safe really reinforcing those things and that could happen therapeutically you know in an office where a foster parent sits down with the foster child and a therapist and the foster parent is ired to share with the child how they are going to be safe why they're going to be taken care of the things that you're going to do to assure them of their

acceptance into the family that they're not going to be an outsider all of those things or a foster parent could just do that at their home but ultimately telling them this is why you're safe and this is why you're going to be okay

here kind of as a followup question to kind of what you said would you say that anxiety plays a prevalent part of a foster child's life while in foster care

I think it absolutely can I think if they're if they're young enough they can probably escape that but at a certain age some anxiety um is absolutely going to be there because of the displacement because of the loss because of the confusion because of the wondering if they're going to be accepted and wondering how this Foster family going to be their emotions are so heightened that they're just they can easily be anxious about just the entire situation so I would say you know likely with foster children you could easily look at anxiety and potentially some mild um depression not that you'd be diagnosed them with like major depressive disorder but um there's a disorder called adjustment disorder and I would say that that would probably be a pretty um fitting um diagnosis because it it can have to do with anxiety and depression in an attempt to adjust to a new situation and so it's it is it can be that anxiety and depression in the adjustment

thank you okay so I'm just going to read you a little bit about Horticultural therapy really quick okay so therapeutic gardening for cultural therapy is a therapy treatment that involves monical gardening exercises these experiences have been shown to reduce stress while promoting over health benefits gardening improves mental health while also improving physical health self-esteem is improved through gardening through children's autonomy and control over plant

mindfulness helps both manage stress while learning regulation techniques to help manage future emotions and then with that in mind would you say that hor cultural therapy practices are appropriate to potentially address challenges brought up within foster care

absolutely if it's going to help them be more mindful um that mindful mindfulness and calming aspects both of those help decrease that anxiety and depression and then another thing well you mentioned giving them control over something which is great because foster children are going to feel very out of control of their situation they're grabbed from what they knew they're put somewhere they they know they're going to feel like any control in their lives is the last thing that they have so giving them some control is a very good idea and then also it allows them to be creative and allows them to express themselves creatively a lot of people plant and garden um I have a lot of clients that do planting and gardening and things like that and that's part of their creative Outlet designing what plants to put where and what colors go where and different things like that so it can be a creative Outlet too which we know automatically that kids tend to be really creative and they respond creatively to Artistic things and so I think it could touch them in that aspect

also awesome thank you and then are there any challenges you foresee happening with this for cultural therapy approach and is there any kind of negatives that would outweigh the positives

I don't think so no because the act itself of of the of the gardening um is there really isn't anything um negative that comes from that whether for even people that aren't in foster care just for adults or other um teenagers or kids that that like to Garden um so I don't think there'd be anything negative from it there's no there's no I don't see any emotional or mental or physical

harm at all I just I think it could be give them that sense of autonomy and and be uh be creative and um a lot lot of people there's just something about getting their hands in the dirt which we know kids are really good at doing anyway so this is sort of like mindful play yes awesome okay that's it see it wasn't really long yeah do you have any other inputs you would like to kind of have on the record for this study

I don't think so

Interview 4

